

Multiple Pitch Perception with Rate-Place Metamers

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Abstract. Pitch is a key perceptual attribute of natural sounds, but its neural basis remains under active debate. The pattern of average neural firing rates along the tonotopic axis, called the rate-place code, adequately explains human pitch perception for most stimuli, including harmonic complex tones (HCTs). However, spectrally denser stimuli, such as mixtures of multiple simultaneous HCTs (i.e., chords) have limited rate-place information due to auditory filtering. Some pitch tasks remain feasible under such conditions, but it is unclear whether listeners rely on weak residual rate-place cues or turn to other cues. To adjudicate between these possibilities, we generated synthetic stimuli we call rate-place metamers (META), which have near-identical rate-place representations to original pitch-evoking stimuli (ORIG) according to an established model of auditory nerve firing (Zilany, Bruce, and Carney, 2014), but are otherwise unconstrained. Temporal representations of ORIG and META stimuli, evaluated via autocorrelation (Meddis and O'Mard, 1997) or neural fluctuations (Vecchi et al., 2022), differed according to F0 and frequency region. In human listeners, we measured F0 difference limens (FODLs) and chord discrimination performance for ORIG and META across a range of F0s and spectral regions. The behavioral results follow broadly similar patterns for ORIG and META, suggesting that rate-place cues are sufficient for multiple pitch perception in most circumstances. However, significant differences did emerge between the two stimulus types in some conditions, indicating contribution of cues other than the rate-place code. Timing-based models also failed to fully explain the behavioral results. Rate-place metamers are a tool that may allow us to measure the proportion of pitch perception attributable to rate-place cues, and so to better understand the neural mechanisms underlying pitch perception.

INTRODUCTION

Pitch, the perceptual correlate of fundamental frequency (F0), is an important cue for sound source segregation and a key organizing feature in speech and music. A large body of evidence supports a rate-place model of pitch perception in humans (Wightman, 1973; Terhardt, 1974; Cedolin and Delgutte, 2005; see Oxenham, 2023 for a recent review). In this model, the tonotopic separation of component frequencies along the basilar membrane produces a pattern of average firing rates in the auditory nerve that provides a cue to frequency content, and thus to pitch. However, due to the limited frequency resolution of human auditory filters, the individual frequency components of spectrally dense stimuli like chords (mixtures of multiple F0s) should be difficult for humans to resolve. Although rate-place representations of chords are degraded, many human listeners can perceive the pitches within these chords without difficulty. However, it is unclear from previous studies (Graves and Oxenham, 2019; Guest and Oxenham, 2022) whether this is achieved using residual rate-place cues, or whether pitch is extracted using other cues.

Given the inconclusive evidence for rate-place supported multiple pitch perception in these past studies, we sought to more directly limit the available neural cues by generating stimuli based only on the information contained in the rate-place representation of a chord, simulated by an established model of auditory nerve firing (Zilany, Bruce, and Carney, 2014). Inspired by previous studies of model metamers in visual (Freeman and Simoncelli, 2011) and auditory (McDermott and Simoncelli, 2011; Feather et al., 2023) perception, our stimuli were *rate-place metamers* of classic pitch-evoking stimuli, being physically distinct from the original stimuli, but with equivalent outputs in a rate-place pitch model. We generated the metamers by starting with noise, so every property of this stimulus other than its rate-

place representation was unconstrained. By multiplying the FFT spectrum of Gaussian noise by the difference in model output between that noise and a target stimulus, and iteratively repeating this process, we were eventually able to make the rate-place representation of the noise match that of the target stimulus.

Beyond the rate-place code, there are also other potential cues for pitch contained in the temporal pattern of the neural response. Many temporal models of pitch perception use the time intervals between phase-locked neural spikes, generally quantified with an autocorrelation function (e.g., Meddis and O'Mard, 1997). More recently, there has also been interest in neural fluctuation profiles (Carney, 2018; Vecchi et al., 2022), quantified as the variability of the neural firing rate at each channel over time, as an additional signal contained in the neural representation of sound. Although we only set out to explicitly match rate-place cues in our metamers, the metamerization process amounts to introducing spectral modulation, which also necessarily affects the temporal pattern of the stimulus. Therefore we also evaluated our metamers in terms of these two temporal models, and found differences in their representations in some stimulus conditions, despite the matched rate-place profiles.

If our modeled rate-place cue contains all the necessary information for pitch perception, human listeners should perform similarly for metamers and original stimuli on a range of behavioral pitch perception tasks and stimulus conditions. On the other hand, wherever behavioral responses diverge between metamers and original stimuli, this suggests that listeners are taking advantage of temporal cues not captured by the rate-place model.

METHODS

Participants

For each task, we recruited normal-hearing human listeners between ages 18 and 25. Listeners were first screened for normal audiometric thresholds (at or below 20 dB HL) at octave frequencies between 250 Hz and 8 kHz. They were then screened using a 2-alternative forced-choice adaptive tracking procedure for thresholds at 14 kHz. The high-frequency screening was a tone-in-noise detection task, and the cutoff for inclusion was a threshold under 40 dB for tones presented with threshold-equalizing noise (TEN) at 35 dB per equivalent rectangular bandwidth (ERB). Participants who failed the high-frequency screening were excluded from the high-frequency portions of Task 1 but were included in analyses for the remainder of the experiment, which did not include task-relevant sounds above 8 kHz. The total number of participants included in analyses is 18, but each participant completed only the tasks for which they passed the pure-tone training procedure (see Procedure), specifically 14 subjects for Tasks 1-2, 13 subjects for Task 3, and 9 subjects for Task 4. Only 6 subjects successfully passed the pure-tone training for all 4 tasks. All participants provided informed consent and were compensated at a rate of \$15 per hour for their participation. Study procedures were approved by IRB # HUM00218552.

Stimuli

Stimuli in the main experiment were divided into two types: original pitch-evoking stimuli (ORIG) and rate-place metamers of those stimuli (META). Stimuli of the ORIG type in Task 1 were broadly inspired by the stimuli used in Mehta & Oxenham (2020). Bandpass-filtered harmonic complex tones (HCTs) were presented, masked by simultaneously gated threshold-equalizing noise (TEN) (Moore et al., 2000). The passband had a low cutoff equal to the 4th, 5th, 7th, 8th, 10th, 11th, 13th, or 14th multiple of the F0, and a high cutoff 9 ranks higher (e.g., at the 13th component when the low cutoff was the 4th). Within the passband, the level per component was 45 dB SPL. Components outside the passband decreased in level by 6 dB per rank. Masking TEN was presented broadband at 35 dB SPL per equivalent rectangular bandwidth (ERB), along with an additional TEN at 40 dB SPL per ERB below the low cutoff, to ensure the F0 region was well masked. ORIG stimuli in Tasks 2-4 were broadly inspired by the stimuli used in Graves & Oxenham (2019). In tasks 2-4, the passband did not depend on F0 but remained constant across a given frequency condition. From low to high, the seven spectral regions tested were: 0.5-2, 0.7-3, 1-4, 1.5-6, 2-6.6, 3-7.2, and 4-8 kHz. Components outside the passband decreased in level by 0.03 dB per Hz (equivalent to 6 dB every 200 Hz).

For every ORIG stimulus in the main experiment, we created its META equivalent by iteratively modifying the FFT spectrum of noise (see Figure 1 for a schematic illustration of this process). We first filtered a sample of Gaussian noise using the same filter parameters as the passband of the ORIG stimulus, with a flat spectrum in the passband and slopes of 6 dB/rank of the corresponding F0 (Task 1) or 0.03 dB/Hz (Tasks 2-4). We added TEN as in the ORIG condition, creating a noise stimulus with the same broad spectral shape as the target ORIG stimulus. We then measured the rate-place representation of the target stimulus and the noise stimulus using an established model simulating firing

at the level of the auditory nerve (Zilany, Bruce, and Carney, 2014). The model responses were generated using low-spontaneous-rate fibers in the humanized variant of the model. For both the noise stimulus and the target stimulus, we measured an auditory nerve average rate (ANAR) response by averaging the instantaneous firing rate over time for 10 samples of 1000 ms each, discarding the first and last 100 ms. The ANAR was measured for a range of characteristic frequencies (CFs) from 300 Hz below the low-frequency cutoff to 300 Hz above the high-frequency cutoff for each stimulus. By subtracting the ANAR of the target ORIG stimulus from the ANAR of the noise stimulus, we obtained a spectral difference function, which was then used as a guide to orient the metamerization process.

FIGURE 1. Left: processing pipeline for generating rate-place metamers (META) from original pitch-evoking stimuli (ORIG). A Gaussian noise stimulus (NOISE) was iteratively modified so that its resulting auditory-nerve average-rate (ANAR) response, according to a model simulation, matched that of the target ORIG stimulus. Right: example stimuli in both META and ORIG conditions, in three different spectral regions (left to right) and F0 regions (top to bottom). The curves above the spectra are auditory-nerve average-rate (ANAR) responses modeled using Zilany, Bruce, and Carney (2014).

On each iteration of the metamerization process, we multiplied the FFT of the noise stimulus by the ANAR difference, at a rate of 0.1 dB SPL per spike per second. The relationship between FFT magnitude and average firing rate has no canonical equivalent, but this chosen rate is analogous to an appropriately slow learning rate in a gradient descent paradigm (such as the one used for metamerization by Freeman and Simoncelli, 2011). This rate allowed the noise stimulus to approach a better approximation of the target ANAR on each iteration, without overshooting due to nonlinear properties of the response. We found that 50 iterations sufficient to ensure metamer ANAR within 1 spike per second of the target ANAR for all measured cochlear channels. See Figure 1 for a comparison of ANARs (near identical) and frequency spectra (visibly different) for ORIG and META across different conditions.

Modeling

For each of three cues, we created an index of “cue strength” based on model responses (see Fig. 4 for results). The strength each pitch cue was indexed as follows: we measured model response to ten pairs of stimuli in each condition, each with F0s one semitone apart, and compared responses against responses to noise. Cue strength was then defined using the root-mean-square (rms) difference between these model responses, specifically as $\text{rms}(\text{Pitch 1} - \text{Pitch 2}) \div \text{rms}(\text{Noise 1} - \text{Noise 2})$. For the rate-place model, the model response was the auditory-nerve average-rate (ANAR) function. The fluctuation model (after Vecchi et al., 2022) takes advantage of the fact that neural firing patterns are steadier at component CFs but fluctuate between components. The fluctuation index was defined as the standard deviation of the envelope of the AN response at each CF, using LSR fibers, normalized by mean firing rate. Cue strength was then derived using the above equation from the function of fluctuation index as a function of CF.

Metamers showed weaker fluctuation cues than original stimuli in certain conditions (see Fig. 2). For the autocorrelation model, we took the summary autocorrelation function (SACF) of each AN response, summing across frequency channels. This cue degrades sharply at high frequencies due to the limit of phase locking. The cue strength then derived using the same equation using the SACF to each stimulus. Metamers largely preserved the autocorrelation cues except for low-F0 unresolved stimuli.

FIGURE 2. Modeling results showing cue strength for each of the three modeled pitch cues, for each of the conditions in the behavioral experiment. In every model, cue strength was quantified using the rms difference between model responses to stimuli spaced 1 semitone apart in F0. The noise baseline is shown as the dashed line for the rate-place and fluctuations model, and in absolute terms as a separate line for the autocorrelation model.

Procedure

The experiment was divided into 4 tasks, each of which measured different aspects of pitch perception or multiple pitch perception. After audiometric screening, participants were given verbal instructions and practice with a training version each of 4 tasks in the main experiment, using pure tones with no masking noise. Training was divided into 5

blocks of 20 trials each, and a participant was determined to have passed the training procedure if they achieved a sensitivity index (d') of 1.5 or higher on any of the 5 training blocks. Otherwise, the participant was deemed to have failed the training procedure, excluding them from participation in the main experiment version of that tasks. Tasks 1 and 2 were yoked such that failing training for either task led to exclusion from the other. For Task 3 and Task 4, passing or failing was independent of other tasks.

FIGURE 3. Results from four behavioral pitch perception tasks using both original pitch-evoking stimuli and their rate-place metamers. The four tasks are in rows from top to bottom, while target F0s are shown from left to right. In tasks 1 and 2, the plotted performance measure is F0DL, where lower DLs reflect greater accuracy. In tasks 3 and 4, the measure is the sensitivity index d' , where higher d' reflects greater accuracy. Throughout: shaded regions ± 1 SEM.

Task 1 measured F0DLs for single pitches and was known to the participants as “Up vs. Down.” On each trial, participants heard two tones, each 500 ms in duration with 30-ms raised-cosine on- and off-ramps, separated by 100 ms of silence. The participants were asked to say whether the direction of the pitch change between the two tones was up or down. The difference in F0 between these two tones, ΔF_0 , was adaptively varied using a 1-up 2-down rule until the sixth reversal at final step size, with each threshold the average of 2 runs per condition in a randomized order.

Task 2 measured F0DLs for a single pitch in the context of a triad, a combination of three simultaneous F0s, and was known to participants as “Up-Up vs. Down-Down.” On each trial, participants heard four sounds, each 500 ms in duration with 30 ms on- and off-ramps, separated by silent gaps of 100 ms between each pair of sounds. Sounds 1 and 3 were single pitches while sounds 2 and 4 were triads in which the tone with the highest pitch was close in F0 to the single pitch on sounds 1 and 3. Participants were asked to compare the reference pitch in sounds 1 and 3 to the target highest pitch in sounds 2 and 4, and say whether the pattern of pitch changes was “up-up” (upwards from sound 1 to 2 and upwards from sound 3 to 4) or “down-down.” Thresholds were the average of 3 runs per condition in a randomized order.

Task 3 measured participants’ accuracy at discriminating different types of triads, requiring listeners to identify all three F0s in the mixture to within 1 semitone precision, and was known to participants as “Major vs. Minor.” This task was adapted from Graves and Oxenham (2019). On each trial, participants heard a single triad and were asked to assign it a label: either Major or Minor.

Task 4 measured participants’ accuracy at chord discrimination in a label-free manner and was known to participants as “Same vs. Different.” On each trial, participants heard a sequence of 8 triads, with a silent pause in the middle. Participants were asked to discriminate between “Same” trials on which the latter 4 triads were an exact transposition, 2 semitones higher, of the first 4, and “Different” trials, on which the final chord was one semitone different in either the highest, middle, or lowest pitch.

RESULTS

The results from the four behavioral tasks are shown in Fig. 3. In Task 1 ($n = 14$), results for ORIG replicate the findings of Mehta and Oxenham (2020): for mid-range F0s like 200 Hz, F0DLs transition from good performance (near 1% $\Delta F0$) to poor performance (near 5% $\Delta F0$) as the lowest included harmonic rank shifts from the 7th-8th to the 10th-11th. However, for very high F0s such as 1400 Hz, this same transition in behavioral performance happens earlier, as lowest rank shifts from 4th-5th to 7th-8th. These transitions happened at the same point for META and ORIG. However, thresholds for META are elevated relative to ORIG thresholds for unresolved pitch.

In Task 2 ($n = 14$), F0DLs are higher across the board compared to the single-pitch Task 1, consistent with findings from Graves and Oxenham (2019). In Task 2, when masked by simultaneous F0s in the context of a triad, F0DLs follow broadly the same pattern for META and ORIG.

In Task 3 ($n = 13$), listeners were required to discriminate all 3 F0s in the mixture to successfully perform the task, at a constant level of stimulus difference. Results are shown in terms of the sensitivity index d' . While there is some overlap between ORIG and META performance, certain conditions, notably the high-frequency mid-F0 conditions (unresolved) show a clear advantage for META over ORIG. This trend is also apparent in the low-F0 conditions, though performance is generally closer to chance for both stimulus types in this region.

Results for Task 4 ($n = 9$), a label-free but more cognitively demanding version of task 3, follow a similar pattern to the results for Task 3, with accuracy notably higher for ORIG than for META in the mid-F0 high-frequency regions, where the rate-place code is least likely to be useful. As in Task 3, the low-F0 stimuli were the most difficult to distinguish for both stimulus types.

DISCUSSION

The behavioral results from human listeners are still preliminary, but so far suggest that metamers overall provide a reasonable match to original stimuli in terms of pitch perception. The replication of previous findings for ORIG stimuli (Graves and Oxenham, 2019; Mehta and Oxenham, 2020) provides a strong baseline against which to measure the results for META stimuli. The overall match between the stimulus types seems to hold true despite the differences in timing representations. There are some notable differences in performance between META and ORIG stimuli for unresolved single pitches (Task 1), suggesting that unresolved pitch is perceived with timing-based cues such as fluctuation or autocorrelation. The possible trend of degraded performance for META in some conditions of Tasks 3 and 4 may reflect multiple pitch using a cue other than the rate-place code, but we hesitate to draw firm conclusions about this before the full dataset is collected.

At this stage, the combination of modeling and behavioral results seems to suggest that it in most circumstances, it is indeed residual rate-place cues that listeners use to perceive pitch in chords, and not some other timing-based cue. However, as data collection continues, this preliminary conclusion is subject to change, and some possible differences are already emerging in certain conditions, though they are not perfectly explained by timing models. We hope that

this technique of model metamerization can more broadly serve as a tool allowing researchers to quantify the contributions of various potential cues for pitch perception, or indeed auditory perception tasks more broadly.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Hauser, Samantha. Written comment] From the data collected so far, do you see that the differences between performance with the ORIG and the META are in the same direction for most/all participants? Perhaps related, the participants excluded from a task may be interesting to think about, especially since many of them were able to complete at least one other task. Do you think it's simply just related to the task design and/or needing more training or is there something different about cues those people are weighing for pitch discrimination? Both questions here are getting at whether individuals, who in a real world scenario would likely have all potential cues available, have different weights for the available cues.

[Graves, Jackson. Written response]. We have included in this revision (below) a figure showing subplots of individual participants for task 1, where we hope readers can appreciate that the direction of the ORIG-META difference was similar for most participants, where they were different at all. Results are similar for tasks 2-4. Our intuition about the fact that some participants were excluded based on poor performance in training is that all of these

tasks may require some degree of expertise (for pitch perception generally, or for Western music theory labels in task 3), and may also be highly cognitively demanding (especially task 4 which requires retaining 8 chords in working memory), and therefore are not feasible, even for simple pure-tone pitch, for many participants. In terms of different weights for different cues, our future plans include developing a Bayesian hierarchical model for these pitch cues, which could allow us to estimate different weights on an individual and population level.

[Hauser, Samantha. Written comment] Tasks 1 through 4 seem to be increasing in complexity, but do they seem to increase in cognitive demand? Do you expect greater difference between ORIG and META in more complex tasks?

[Graves, Jackson. Written response]. We think task 4 was exceptionally cognitively demanding, explaining in part why few participants were able to pass the training for this task. However, we do not see any reason to expect high cognitive load to affect the difference between ORIG and META, since these stimuli mainly differ in the reliability of low-level perceptual cues, rather than high-level cognitive constraints.

[Allen, Jont. Oral question] I believe I did an experiment similar to this. I looked into it and I believe there's an explanation for pitch JNDs which is based on high-frequency slope, since we can't synchronize about 4-5 kHz, something like that, so you can't use a cycle by cycle explanation, but Fletcher and other people showed – I can't remember the history of this, but I knew it a long time ago if that counts – the steepness of the skirt above a few kHz goes up to like 5 dB/octave. So it requires that the tone you're trying to estimate has to be high enough that it's well above threshold, and then the JND is really converted into an intensity JND. And the intensity JND and the pitch JND are in agreement, so there's strong support for this idea. And I just rediscovered it and read the literature. So I think if you look at that you'll see that this is explained and makes sense, and blah blah blah.

[Graves, Jackson. Oral response] Thank you, I'll look into that.

[Graves, Jackson. Written response] We believe this comment may have been suggesting that participants could have listened to spectral edges and completed the task by doing level discrimination. This is not possible with our stimuli, because we roved the lowest harmonic rank in task 1 and used frozen spectral envelope in tasks 2-4.

[Charaziak, Karolina. Oral question] Very nice talk, I did not know about metamers before, so that's cool. But I have two questions. The first question is how much did it matter for your model and experimental data to match in d-prime? Because just by eyeballing, I felt your first experiment really matched the best your fluctuation result.

[Graves, Jackson. Oral response] That is a good point, and I see why you say that. It seems like, especially in absolute terms, our behavioral d primes are on the order of 1, for the best conditions, which is about what the fluctuations is predicting. So, point taken, and I don't want to do too much special pleading. But I will say that from my point of view it's better for this kind of model to have better performance than human listeners, because there's all kinds of noise in these behavioral measurements – reasons you might say the wrong thing, you're just confused about the task, you're hitting the wrong button, you're not getting perfect performance – that isn't included in the model, so it should really be an upper bound. And I would also say that the effect of spectral region here, where people are really degrading to chance performance steeply when you go up – that isn't really captured by the fluctuation model, at least in these data so far. But it's a good point, so thanks.

[Charaziak, Karolina. Oral question] And another question, it's probably more naïve, I just don't remember that from my psychoacoustic classes. So, we know that for harmonic complexes, you can have this phenomenon of missing fundamental. It looks like for your original stimuli it was more harmonic, and for the metamers it was less, so did you see a difference, or did you see that at all? Did it play a role?

[Graves, Jackson. Oral response] So actually, all of the pitch, and I kind of skipped over this, but all of the stimuli – it's all missing-fundamental pitch in this experiment for originals and metamers, because we want to make sure that people are really extracting the pitch and not just listening to that one frequency of the fundamental. So the F0 is actually not present in any of these sounds, even the original, and it's masked by noise, so you're only hearing from minimum the 2nd harmonic component, but thank you.

[Supplemental figure showing data from individual participants for task 1]

